

РАЗДЕЛ. ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫЕ НАУКИ

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6368634>

UDC 66.094.37: 547, 313.4: 547.3

THE STUDY OF PROPYLENE OXYDATION PROCESS IN THE
PRECENCE OF $\text{Mo}_4\text{Sb}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{1.0}\text{O}_x$ OXIDE ELEMENTS

A.S. Guseynov,

Azerbaijan State University of Oil and Industry,

E-mail: adigozal.huseynov@mail.ru

Annotation: Catalyst for oxidation process of saturated and uncaptured hydrocarbons have been completely studied completely. Due to uncompleted research of the propylene oxidation by help of catalyst selection of the effective catalyst for this process is very actual problem. By this purpose the $\text{Mo}_4\text{Sb}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{1.0}\text{O}_x$ catalytic system have been prepared the activity of this system and influence of oxide element on it is composition have been studied. Based on the influence selectivity of the propylene oxidation process and on the above mentioned results, it is not practically to make certain conclusion .But it is possible to conclude that addition of phosphorus in all systems will increase the selectivity.

Keywords: oxidation, propylene, acrolein, catalyst, acrylic acid

At present, there are no general principles for the selection of effective catalysts for the oxidation of saturated and unsaturated hydrocarbons. The available literature on this issue is all unlimited and basically comes down to patent data. There is a semi-empirical rule that if on one contact (a) the reaction proceeds selectively, but with low activity, and on the other (c) – with greater activity, adding with low selectivity, to (a) a certain amount (c) or vice versa, it is possible expect an increase in both selectivity and activity [1-3].

Since the process of propylene oxidation is practically not fully understood, in order to find the basic principles for the selection of effective catalysts for this process, it was first necessary to investigate the catalytic properties of individual metal oxides.

Investigations of the process of direct oxidation of propylene to acrolein were carried out under laboratory conditions in a flow reactor with a fixed catalyst bed. The best results for the yield of acrolein were obtained on the catalyst $\text{Mo}_4\text{Sb}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{1.0}\text{O}_x$. During the oxidation of propylene over $\text{Mo}_4\text{Sb}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{1.0}\text{O}_x$, the selectivity for acrolein was 3.5 % at a conversion of – 2.6 %. In order to increase the efficiency of this catalyst, phosphorus and cesium were introduced into its

composition. The results of the influence of these cations on the catalytic properties of catalysis are presented in Figures 1-4.

As can be seen from Figure 1, the addition of phosphorus to the $\text{Mo}_4\text{Sb}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{1.0}\text{O}_x$ system has little effect on the activity, but increases the selectivity at a phosphorus content of 1.5 wt%.

A further increase in the phosphorus content leads to a uniform decrease in the selectivity for acrolein.

Figure 1 – Effect of the amount of phosphorus on catalytic properties $\text{Mo}_4\text{Sb}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{1.0}\text{O}_x$ catalytic system in the reaction of propylene oxidation 1,2,4,5-selectivity, respectively, for acrolein; CO_2 ; CO and acetic acid; 3-conversion of propylene. Temperature 350°C contact time 3.0 s. Supply of reagents propylene: $\text{O}_2 : \text{H}_2\text{O} = 0.6 : 1.1 : 1.8$

Figure 2 – Influence of the amount of phosphorus on catalytic properties $\text{Mo}_4\text{Sb}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{1.0}\text{O}_x$ catalytic system in the reaction of propylene oxidation 1,2,4,5-selectivity, respectively, for acrolein; CO_2 ; CO and acetic acid; 3-conversion of propylene . Temperature 350°C contact time 3.0 sec. Supply of reagents propylene: O_2 : H_2O = 0.6: 1.1: 1.8

Phosphorus additions to the $\text{Mo}_4\text{Sb}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{1.0}\text{O}_x$ catalyst are also shown in Figure 2 have little effect on the change in activity, and the selectivity for acrolein increases with increasing phosphorus concentration [4-6].

Figure 3 – Influence of the amount of cesium on the catalytic properties $\text{Mo}_4\text{Sb}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{1.0}\text{O}_x$ catalytic system in the reaction of propylene oxidation 1,2,4,5-selectivity, respectively, for acrolein; CO_2 ; CO and acetic acid; 3-conversion of propylene. Temperature 350°C contact time 3.0 s. Supply of reagents propylene: O_2 : H_2O = 0.6: 1.1: 1.8

Cesium additions to $\text{Mo}_4\text{Sb}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{1.0}\text{O}_x$ catalysts Figure 3 greatly reduces the selectivity for acrolein, and the activity at low concentrations of the promoter in this case increases at 3.5 at% Cs.

Figure 4 – Influence of the amount of cesium on catalytic properties $\text{Mo}_4\text{Sb}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{1.0}\text{O}_x$ catalytic system in the reaction of propylene oxidation 1,2,4,5-selectivity, respectively, for acrolein; CO_2 ; CO and acetic acid; 3-conversion of propylene. Temperature 350°C contact time 3.0 s. Supply of reagents propylene: $\text{O}_2 : \text{H}_2\text{O} = 0.6 : 1.1 : 1.8$

Cs additions to $\text{Mo}_4\text{Sb}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{1.0}\text{O}_x$ system Figure 4 act in a similar way, only the drop in selectivity is more pronounced here.

Figure 5 – Influence of the amount of Cu on the catalytic properties

Mo₄Sb_{0.5}Ni_{1.0}O_x catalytic system in the reaction of propylene oxidation 1,2,4,5-selectivity, respectively, for acrolein; CO₂; CO and acetic acid; 3-conversion of propylene. Temperature 350 °C contact time 3.0 s. Supply of reagents propylene: O₂; H₂O = 0.6: 1.1: 1.8

We tried to improve the catalytic properties of the Mo₄Sb_{0.5}Ni_{1.0}O_x catalyst by introducing copper instead of Cs into its composition; the results obtained in Figure 5 showed that additives, Cu negatively affect the catalytic properties of this contact, namely, lead to a more significant drop in the selectivity to acrolein [7-8]. The nature of the action of Cu additives turned out to be similar to the action of Cs additives. On the basis of the above results, it is practically impossible to draw an unambiguous conclusion regarding the effect of additives on the selectivity of propylene oxidation processes. But it can be said with some certainty that the addition of phosphorus will increase the selectivity in all systems.

Список литературы

- [1] Huseynov A.S. Comparison of the reactivity of some aldehydes and acids in oxidation reactions. / A.S. Huseynov. // Ecoenergetics – Scientific – Technical Journal. Baku, 2018. No. 1. 62-65 pp.
- [2] Huseynov A.S. Research of catalytic properties of the system Mo-Te-M-O_x in reaction oxidation of methylacroleine. / A.S. Huseynov. // 3 rd International Turkic World Confernece on Chemical Sciences and Technologies, Baku Turkey. 13-17 September. 319 p.
- [3] Molybdenum – antimony oxide catalysts in the oxidation of propylene and isobutylene. / A.S. Huseynov Ch. Sh. Ibragimov A.S. Bayramova. // Materials of the VIII Baku International Mammadaliyev Conference on Petrochemistry. – 2012.
- [4] Попов К., Захарьева Е. Лидеры мира полиуретанов. / К. Попов, Е. Захарьева. // Сибур Сегодня. 2009. № 1. 22-23 с.
- [5] Способ производства окиси пропилена: пат. 2008102528 Рос. Федерация. № 20080102528, заявл. 20.06.2006, опубл. 10.08.2009.
- [6] Способ получения пропиленоксида из пропилена и пероксида водорода: пат. 2372343 Рос. Федерация. № 20080108337, заявл. 03.03.2008, опубл. 10.11.2009.
- [7] Process for producing propylene oxide: пат. 2430009. № 20100715902, заявл. 05.05.2010, опубл. 21.03.2012.
- [8] Method for the production of propylene oxide: пат. 0202544. № 2001EP07716, заявл. 05.07.2001, опубл. 10.01.2002.

Bibliography (Transliterated)

[1] Huseynov A.S. Comparison of the reactivity of some aldehydes and acids in oxidation reactions. /A.S. Huseynov. // Ecoenergetics – Scientific – Technical Journal. Baku, 2018. No. 1. 62-65 p.

[2] Huseynov A.S. Research of catalytic properties of the system Mo-Te-M-Ox in reaction oxidation of methylacroleine. /A.S. Huseynov. // 3rd International Turkic World Conference on Chemical Sciences and Technologies, Baku Turkey. 13-17 September. 319 p.

[3] Molybdenum – antimony oxide catalysts in the oxidation of propylene and isobutylene. /A.S. Huseynov Ch. Sh. Ibragimov A.S. Bayramova. // Materials of the VIII Baku International Mammadaliyev Conference on Petrochemistry. – 2012.

[4] Popov K., Zakhariyeva E. Leaders of the polyurethane world. / K. Popov, E. Zakharyeva. // Sibur Today. 2009. No. 1. 22-23 p.

[5] Method for the production of propylene oxide: US Pat. 2008102528 Ros. Federation. No. 20080102528, Appl. 06/20/2006, publ. 08/10/2009.

[6] Method for producing propylene oxide from propylene and hydrogen peroxide: Pat. 2372343 Ros. Federation. No. 20080108337, Appl. 03/03/2008, publ. 11/10/2009.

[7] Process for producing propylene oxide: Pat. 2430009. No. 20100715902, claim. 05/05/2010, publ. 03/21/2012.

[8] Method for the production of propylene oxide: Pat. 0202544. No. 2001EP07716, Appl. 07/05/2001, publ. 01/10/2002.

© A.S. Guseynov, 2022

Поступила в редакцию 5.01.2022
Принята к публикации 25.01.2022

Для цитирования:

Guseynov A.S. The study of propylene oxydation process in the precence of Mo₄Sb_{0,5}Ni_{1,0}O_x oxide elements // Инновационные научные исследования. 2022. № 1-3(15). С. 6-12. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>